

ISic1023

I.Sicily inscription 1023

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140502

1. Διὸς

2. Ἀγο#⁷ραίου ²⁶Ἀγοραίου? ²⁶{²⁷Α[κ]ραίου}²⁷

3.

Edition: PHI175424

1. Διὸς

2. [Ακ]ραίου.

3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492651

EDCS 39102177

PHI 140502

PHI 175424

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0203 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L. (eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.14

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